

Substituted 2-Sulphanilamidoazoacetates and Their Cyclisation

Anil Prakash and I. R. Gambhir

Ethyl acetoacetate reacts with diazotised solution of 2-sulphanilamidobenzenes and sulphanilamides¹. It has now been observed that it also reacts with 2-sulphanilamido-thiazoles, -pyridine, -pyrimidine, -pyrazine etc., irrespective of the nature of the heterocyclic nuclei, to yield the corresponding 2-sulphanilamidoazoacetates. When heated with dilute hydrochloric acid, these undergo hydrolysis, followed by decarboxylation, to yield 2-sulphamidophenylhydrazones of α -ketopropaldehyde. On treatment with carbonylic reagents, such as semicarbazide acetate, phenylhydrazine, hydroxylamine acetate, etc., these form pyrazolone-amide, pyrazolone, and isoxazolone derivatives, which are yellow to orange in colour.

Procedure.—The diazotised solution of substituted 2-sulphanilamides (0.01*M*) was shaken vigorously with the cooled mixture of sodium acetate (0.7*M*), ethyl acetoacetate (0.01*M*), water (25 ml), and ethanol (25 ml). The products on recrystallisation from acetic acid afforded 70-80% of 2-sulphanilamidoazoacetates in yellow needles. On heating with HCl (dil.) in ethanol, these were converted into 2-sulphamidophenylhydrazones of α -ketopropaldehyde, recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	2-Sulphanilamido- ...azoacetate.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		2,4-DNP M.P.	M.P.	2-Sulphamidophenylhydrazones of α -ketopropaldehyde.	
				Found.	Reqd.			Formula.	%Sulphur. Found. Reqd.
1	-thiazole-	155°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ S ₂	16.00	16.16	255°	305°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₄ S ₂	19.87 19.75
2	-methylthiazole-	181°	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₄ S ₂	15.50	15.61	233°	316°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S ₂	18.84 18.93
3	-pyridine-	170°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₄ S	8.09	8.20	213° ^b	311°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	10.00 10.06
4	-pyrimidine-	105°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	8.09	8.18	214°	286°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.94 10.03
5	-4-methyl- pyrimidine-	143°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	7.83	7.90	208°	300°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.52 9.61
6	-4,6-dimethyl- pyrimidine-	172°	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃ S	7.53	7.63	250°	302°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.17 9.22
7	-pyrazine-	180°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	8.10	8.18	246°	314°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.94 10.02

1. Prakash and Gambhir, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 847; 1964, 41, 133.

2-Sulphanilamidoazoacetates (0.01M) on refluxing separately with semicarbazide acetate, phenylhydrazine, hydrazine hydrate, and hydroxylamine acetate (0.01M) in ethanol and acetic acid cyclised to 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-pyrazolone-1-amide, 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-pyrazolones, 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-pyrazolones, and 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-isoxazolones, respectively, reported in Tables II and III.

TABLE II

3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-pyrazolone-1-amides.					1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-pyrazolones.					
*No.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.				Found.	Reqd.
1	275°	68%	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	15.58	15.72	219°	74%	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	14.48	14.54
2	280°	66	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	15.10	15.20	225°	74	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	14.00	14.09
3	280°	66	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₇ S	7.88	7.98	227°	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₆ S	7.26	7.37
4	225°	69	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₈ S	7.87	7.96	222°	72	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₇ S	7.27	7.35
5	240°	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₈ S	7.72	7.69	231°	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₇ S	7.00	7.12
6	260°	64	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₈ S	7.30	7.44	242°	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₇ S	6.80	6.91
7	215°	67	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₈ S	7.68	7.96	210°	73	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₇ S	7.25	7.35

*As recorded in Table I.

TABLE III

3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-pyrazolones.					3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-isoxazolones.				
*No.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.	
1	275°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	17.50	17.58	240°	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂	17.44	17.53	
2	280°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	16.84	16.93	246°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₅ S ₂	16.80	16.88	
3	260°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	8.95	8.93	200°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₅ S	8.81	8.91	
4	270°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₇ S	8.82	8.91	235°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	8.80	8.88	
5	260°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₇ S	8.43	8.57	229°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₆ S	8.48	8.55	
6	245°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₇ S	8.18	8.26	205°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₆ S	8.12	8.24	
7	254°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₇ S	8.80	8.91	227°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	8.77	8.88	

*As recorded in Table I.

Thanks of the authors are due to Drs. G. Weiler and F. B. Strauss, England, for microanalyses.